

Communicating cultural and creative spaces: Recommendations to promote sustainability and citizen participation.

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Credits

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Declaration of authorship

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About the research

These recommendations are part of original research, framed in the project of the 2018 Spanish R&D Plan: "Art, Architecture and Heritage in the processes of building the new cultural territories' image (from Districts to Territories)", Ref. PGC2018-094351-B-C43, funded by the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities.

The complete study has been published by Fragua publishing house, under the title *City-branding. Fundamentals and Brand Applications in Cultural and Creative Spaces* (2021), written by Jennifer García Carrizo.

This document contains a set of recommendations for practical application by managers, actors, institutions, teachers and researchers linked to creative and cultural industries.

Key elements to promote sustainability and citizen participation

When communicating and working on the development of strategies for the sustainability and citizen participation in cultural and creative spaces, it is essential to consider the following 4 key elements:

1. **Characteristics of the space.**
2. **Mixed uses** of the space.
3. **Heritage** associated to the place.
4. Creative and cultural **audiences.**

The characteristics of the space

Understanding the history and analyzing the location, character and identity of the place is especially relevant.

History

- History determines how a space has been built and helps us **understand the space itself, as well as its origins and the reason why it was created.**
- Knowing how the space has evolved is essential to understanding the **identity of the place.**

Location

- It is transcendental to understand the nature of **the environment** of the cultural and creative space, where it is located with respect to the city center and to identify the **neighboring population centers**: What are they like? What kinds of people live in them? Who visits them?
- The **unclear borders** of the space must be valued. Even if you are working in a very specific and defined space, this place must relate to other actors that are outside it. This guarantees its integration with the environment and its collaboration with other spaces at a regional, national, or even international level. **Remember that collaborations always add up!**

The space character and identity

How is this space different from other cultural and creative spaces? What does this space contribute to, differently from others? It is necessary to look for the **defining characteristics of the space and its unique character**; otherwise, urban spaces can end up falling into monotony, looking the same as others. The important thing is to know what differentiates the space we are talking about: a building?, a square? Does it have any symbolic or representative element that other "similar" spaces do not have?

The importance of mixed uses

The term “mixed uses” refers to the fact that, despite speaking of cultural and creative spaces, not only cultural and creative institutions and industries are relevant in them. Other kinds of actors make it possible for these spaces to be appropriate for "living, working or educating and playing", such as restaurants, sports areas, open-air green areas, residential spaces and educational institutions, among others linked to leisure and habitability. Remember: **all these spaces and actors are "catalysts" contributing to the sustainability and development of the area!**

In this sense, it is important to consider the activities and interests of the people who inhabit the area. From a gender perspective, to promote greater inclusion of women, the specific dynamics in which they are involved must also be considered. For example, women are usually the main care providers for groups in vulnerable situations. Therefore, adequate conditions for women to have a full experience and truly enjoy the spaces must be guaranteed.

All actors linked to creativity and culture are the "anchors" of these spaces, but this "anchor" work must turn them into cooperating actors that configure spaces where social cohesion, economic growth and a sense of belonging are fostered. They must work in harmony with secondary actors and generate a joint "value chain" with them.

It would be useless for an art gallery to exist in an area where there are no leisure alternatives that make the space used during all hours of the day. The presence of secondary actors, such as bars, restaurants and other types of leisure spaces helps the mix of uses of the area and, consequently, guarantees the social mix and helps to avoid urban problems such as segregation and insecurity.

Heritage associated to the place

Heritage is made up of all those **tangible and intangible elements** whose conservation is fundamental, for they are part of the culture of the space and have a historical, technological, social, architectural, or scientific value.

Tangible heritage (industrial spaces, historical routes, monuments, historical sites, architecture, movable and immovable property, etc.) is fundamental, but so is the intangible (traditions, stories, festivals, rituals or stories and memories linked to a space).

An efficient public policy on the matter promotes the harmonization of both elements and, at the same time, allows them to coexist with the specific needs of the different population groups of the site: women, people with disabilities, girls, boys and adolescents, elderly people, etc.

Managing institutions and actors of cultural and creative spaces not only has to focus on “hard” assets but also on the “soft” ones: how can we preserve the memories of the people who inhabit these spaces? How can we recover the sounds and the characteristic smells of a place?

Audiences, a fundamental element in sustainability and citizen participation

When managing a space, one must consider **who it is managed for**. Who are their audiences? Even better, **who uses the space**?

Traditionally, cultural, and creative spaces have been focused on as tourist areas. However, they can be presented as spaces for **social cohesion and citizen participation** where the different stakeholders can develop their concerns and needs. Also, they should be presented as places that can reflect the identities of a variety of groups (usually absorbed by the mainstream). Thus, the representation and visualization of women, for example, are vital for the creation of spaces in which these realities coexist.

The three target audiences whose participation is transcendental in the configuration and conservation of a cultural and creative space are its **inhabitants and those of the city in which it is framed, its workers and tourists**. To all of them, we must add the local and regional educational and government institutions, other cultural actors or those linked to the creative industries at the local and regional level, potential investors in the area, suppliers in the area and the potential residents of the space in question.

In addition, **while facilitating the calling for new audiences to ensure the diversity of the area, existing audiences must be maintained**. The latter will avoid, among other things, the gentrification of the area.

More information at...

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